

Generating logical summaries for the detection of rare genetic diseases

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Abstract

Rare diseases affect between 27 and 36 million people according to the European Commission. Research on rare genetic diseases is reported in manually-curated databases such as OMIM: Online Mendelian Inheritance in Man. However, it can be argued that the OMIM webpages are too lengthy for the clinician to derive an appropriate diagnostic in a short amount of time. In this project, named *OMIMSummarize* and presented at the D4Gen Hackathon by Genopole in March, 2024 in Paris, we explore the possible ways of generating logical summaries for OMIM webpages, in order to help clinicians perform computationally-guided analyses of symptoms. This work contributes to the cause of developing formal and explainable artificial intelligence, rather than mis-using Large Language Models and conversational agents which are able to hallucinate summaries on-the-fly. Ultimately, the goal would be to have the information from the OMIM database in logical relationship form, so that we could derive verifiable diagnoses using only those logical relationships.

Background

Large Language Models (LLMs), are a form of generative Artificial Intelligence (AI), which are used to perform an incredible variety of text-based tasks through their capacity of processing and generating new text. Conversational agents such as chatbots famously make use of LLMs in order to answer to user prompts, making use of the knowledge and techniques developed in the field of Natural Language Processing (NLP) (Yandell & Majoros, 2002). Among famous chatbots available to the general public, let us cite the high-performing ChatGPT, Google Gemini, Microsoft Copilot and Mistral Chat. Medics and physicians are looking more and more into using such popular chatbots for disease diagnosis and evaluation, in the advent of a new era in medicine referred to as digital health (Lupton, 2013).

OMIM (Online Mendelian Inheritance in Man) is an online text database listing genes and phenotypes associated with hereditary diseases in humans (Hamosh et al., 2005). Its website lists rare congenital diseases, and describes each disease, gene and phenotype using short summaries describing the state of knowledge on the subject, accompanied by hand-selected citations based on conclusive experimental results. Founded and maintained by John Hopkins Hospital (Baltimore, USA), OMIM is a reference resource with many uses to clinicians, by providing exhaustive documentation on pathologies with a genetic component.

Further database initiatives exist, such as the Franco-European OrphaNet project (Pavan et al., 2017). While OMIM provides longer, highly documented pages with substantial research data and a history of the discoveries about the diseases, OrphaNet provides shorter pages and aims to be clear on treatment methods and statistics such as prevalences, even though those might not be consensual. Indeed, OMIM pages suffer from being too lengthy, which clinicians might not appreciate as they would be looking for an immediate, applicable diagnosis and treatment. For instance, Duchenne muscular dystrophy (entry [#310200](#)) contains no less than 15k words across 150 paragraphs, excluding the 227 references.

From these considerations, it becomes clear that clinicians will be tempted to ask a conversational agent to perform the summary for them. And indeed, the text summary task is, among the other daily tasks that one could be asking ChatGPT, one of the most natural ones a

physician could ask a Natural Language Processing system (Goh et al., 2024; Hager et al., 2024). Still, the authors here argue that, unless specialized methodology for summarizing uniquely from the text is used, and rigorously scientifically evaluated, this is a 'wrong good idea'. As an instance, the protein domains summaries generated by LLMs in the most recent release of InterPro are, from a user perspective, factitious and misleading (Paysan-Lafosse et al., 2025). What the average user doesn't realize is, behind the technical prowess, our favorite chatbots operate black-box on undisclosed proprietary parameters and data, some natural and some synthetic (Jordon et al., 2022), so making the prompt and discussion public will not be enough to attribute credit and causation to the chatbot's responses. They are by-nature unexplainable.

Therefore, what clinicians can rely on should be one of the following: 1) manually-written and manually-curated summaries, such as the ones from the aforementioned OMIM database, 2) automatically-generated summaries, but with failsafes so that all of the textual elements originate only from such manually-curated sources. This implies that words including medical terms can only be reformulated with validated synonyms. For instance, characterisation of the content of biological databases is now possible with "ontologies" (Collier et al., 2015; Robinson et al., 2008), elements of logical semantics defining, among other relationships, synonyms, and enabling complex queries. In particular, one could summarize a text by decomposing all of its syntactic elements into logical relationships (Bast & Hausmann, 2013), such as ontologies, then automatically process said logical relationships. Thus, taking from this idea, our project proposes to automatically generate accurate and targeted logical summaries of the OMIM database for the clinician.

Aim of the project

An automated text analysis or 'text-mining' approach enables automatic interpretation of textual data, aided by ontologies which list, among other things, all the synonyms associated with a gene, a phenotype or a patient (Collier et al., 2015; Yandell & Majoros, 2002). Here, rather than ontologies, we will model logical relationships by logical rules of logical programming, which are conceptually different but similar in utilization. For instance, a synonym might be modelled by the logical rules: `is(a, synonym_a) AND is(synonym_a, a)`. The aim of this project is to derive logical rules specific to or common to each OMIM entry, in order to facilitate their interpretation by an automatic reasoning tool. We are interested in the problem of generating logical predicates L , ordered relations (tuples), between n elements $L(1, \dots, i, \dots, n)$ from an OMIM webpage.

For example, the very short OMIM entry [#203760](#) could be summarised as follows:

```
description(203760, "Meigel et al.(1974)","new connective tissue disorder").
patient(203760,"Meigel et al.(1974)","son of consanguineous parents aged 10").
similar(203760, phenotype("clinical and radiologic abnormalities"),
        both("Marfan syndrome", "osteogenesis imperfecta")).
show(203760, in("Study of cultured fibroblasts"),
      fail("synthesis", "alpha-2 chains of collagen")).
```

Here, each sentence has been summarised by logical predicates, starting with the OMIM identifier [#203760](#), in order to link the information to the disease. It is of course possible to imagine descriptions that further decompose the sentences syntaxes. The success of the challenge will therefore require a good literature review in order to identify state-of-the-art techniques for decomposing sentences into logical relations (Bast & Hausmann, 2013).

The challenge would be successful with the development of a Python tool capable of converting each OMIM entry into a set of logical rules describing as precisely as possible the textual content of the web page. Similarity with the initial text will be evaluated and any discrepancy between the rules generated and the content must be strictly avoided.

Long-term, one could want a knowledge base of the complete OMIM database using only the same terms, or synonyms. For instance, the predicate `fail("synthesis", "collagen")` could be shared not only by [#203760](#) but also by many other pages. These matches are what

will enable new algorithms to detect similarities between genes using our text-mining approach. As well, this would allow clinicians to perform diagnoses based on symptoms, *e.g.* which rare diseases are associated to patients with a deficient collagen synthesis.

Proof of concept

Automated diagnosis from symptoms summarized from OMIM would then be performed using automated reasoning techniques, *i.e.* logic programming. Let us take for instance the much longer OMIM page [#613679](#), for the hypoprothrombinemia disease.

Hypoprothrombinemia is a rare inherited coagulation disorder characterized by an abnormally low level (< 200 mg/L) of prothrombin (or factor II, a glycoprotein synthesized by the liver) in the blood, resulting in impaired hemostasis and absence of coagulation during wound formation.

It can manifest itself as severe bleeding: nosebleeds, muscle bleeds and, in women, bleeding that persists after childbirth.

Here is an example of logical relationships that could be derived from a summary of the OMIM webpage into logic links:

```
symptom(hypoprothrombinemia, severe_bleeding).
symptom(hypoprothrombinemia, umbilical_bleeding).
gender_symptom(hypoprothrombinemia, severe_menorrhagia, woman_patient).
```

And here is an example of logic links observed by a clinician on a patient:

```
patient_symptom(severe_menorrhagia, patient).
patient_symptom(umbilical_bleeding, patient).
patient_gender(woman_patient, patient).
```

Using the following *s*(CASP) logic programming program (Arias et al., 2018), we could infer whether a patient can have a disease based on their symptoms:

```
can_have(Disease, Patient) :- patient_symptom(Symptom, Patient),
                               symptom(Disease, Symptom).
can_have(Disease, Patient) :- patient_symptom(Symptom, Patient),
                               gender_symptom(Disease, Symptom, Gender),
                               patient_gender(Gender, Patient).
```

Asking *s*(CASP) if the patient can be affected by hypoprothrombinemia returns yes.

```
? can_have(hypoprothrombinemia, patient)
> true
```

Further, combining *s*(CASP) and the interactive Prolog solver SWISH (Sartor et al., 2022; Wielemaker et al., 2015, 2021), we can visualize the explication of the returned answer with natural language, see Figure 1. Assigning all logic links to natural language, *e.g.* `can_have(Disease, Patient)` becomes “Patient Patient can have disease Disease.”, we obtain a full textual explanation of the diagnosis, *i.e.* an output similar to a chatbot’s, but fully explainable.

Many logic programming tools exist. Here we are using the logic programming syntax and tool of *s*(CASP) (Arias et al., 2018). However, worth mentioning are the Prolog languages and solvers (Colmerauer & Roussel, 1996), and Answer Set Programming, another form of logic programming solved with state-of-the-art solver Clingo (Gebser et al., 2012).

In particular, one other form of logic programming is probabilistic logic programming. Such automated reasoning is possible with the ProbLog extension to Prolog (Dries et al., 2015). Since the task of retrieving a summary of logic links from a webpage is complex, requiring exact algorithmic, deterministic ways of determining logic links contained in sentences, one could imagine instead just providing probabilities that a logic link is present in the curated text.

The screenshot shows the SWISH Prolog environment. The main window contains the following code:

```

1 :- use_module(library(scasp)).
2
3
4 #pred symptom(A, B) :: "Disease @(A) has symptom @(B)".
5 #pred patient_symptom(A, B) :: "Patient @(B) has symptom @(A)".
6 #pred patient_gender(A, B) :: "Patient @(B) has gender @(A)".
7 #pred gender_symptom(D, S, G) :: "Disease @(D) has symptom @(S) for gender @(G)".
8 #pred can_have(D, P) :: "Patient @(P) can have disease @(D)".
9
10 symptom(hypoprothrombinemia, severe_bleeding).
11 symptom(hypoprothrombinemia, umbilical_bleeding).
12 gender_symptom(hypoprothrombinemia, severe_menorrhagia, woman_patient).
13
14 patient_symptom(severe_menorrhagia, patient).
15 patient_symptom(umbilical_bleeding, patient).
16 patient_gender(woman_patient, patient).
17
18 can_have(Disease, Patient) :- patient_symptom(Symptom, Patient),
19                               symptom(Disease, Symptom).
20 can_have(Disease, Patient) :- patient_symptom(Symptom, Patient),
21                               gender_symptom(Disease, Symptom, Gender),
22                               patient_gender(Gender, Patient).
23

```

The execution console shows the following results:

```

? can_have(hypoprothrombinemia, patient).
true

? can_have(hypoprothrombinemia, patient).
false

```

The justification for the 'false' result is shown below:

```

? can_have(hypoprothrombinemia, patient).
?-

```

Figure 1: Swish visualization of the ideal s(CASP) program to be generated on case-by-case basis.

For instance, $0.99:\text{patient_symptom}(\text{severe_menorrhagia}, \text{patient})$ signifies there is a 99% certainty that this relationship is in the text. As a result, the diagnostics would also be pondered by probabilities: $0.99:\text{can_have}(\text{hypoprothrombinemia}, \text{patient})$.

Generally, Natural Language Processing tools tasked of retrieving logic links between syntactic objects would often use a scoring system. This score is a very needed feature for evaluating pertinence. For instance, in our experience the NLP technique of BiotXplorer found a weak-scored relationship that was actually two sentential clauses distant by many enumerations, but regrouped together since it was technically the same sentence (Ruch et al., 2024).

Ultimately, by working with these logic links, unannotated, or annotated with probabilities, or with scores, we could be building towards making an explainable artificial intelligence system, since the way to retrieve diagnoses would be purely formally and mathematically solved.

Hackathon results

We separated the project in three phases. The first phase consists in summarizing the webpage information into synthetic, intuitive and targeted logic links for the clinician. The second consists in manually or automatically verifying the validity of the previously generated commands, checking their relevance, precision and accuracy as per the clinician's request. Finally, the third phase consists in using our newly created knowledge base to perform explainable automated reasoning, helping clinicians with diagnoses. We illustrated the third phase earlier with s(CASP).

During the Hackathon itself, we only focused on the first two phases. More precisely, the following tasks were accomplished:

- devised a LLMs-based system summarizing OMIM webpages into logic links (first phase)
- explored the various access methods to LLMs and code reproducibility using interactive notebooks (first phase)
- compared different LLMs to see which gave the better summaries (first/second phase)
- evaluated the results of the summaries (second phase) to see if:
 1. they matched information from the original text, and
 2. they are usable for automated reasoning in the third phase
- identified key research and industry partners for collaboration (second phase)

The first phase was realized by retrieving a summary of logic links with generative AI on our example page, [#613679](#), for disease hypoprothrombinemia. We choose HuggingFace as our provider for Large Language Models and MistralAI for a fast, transparent, French-developed solution (Jiang et al., 2023). Compared to other available LLMs, the API of MistralAI was the easiest to use, although requiring an API token since not completely free. We tried out GPT-2, but were limited by its restriction of 50 characters – the tool did not finish its sentences. Our tests were reported in a Jupyter notebook for reproducibility.

For the second phase, we reviewed the generated logic links and found that they could already be used to construct a knowledge base, although the method still has lots of room for improvement. As a possible research & industry partner, we identified AFM Telethon. The second phase will be a key phase, as it will enable any inaccuracies to be corrected by a clinician.

We were able to design a good attempt at a prompt for generating logic links from OMIM summaries. The prompt goes as follows:

You are given the following text to summarize: "*{paragraph}*". You can only answer with logical relationships of the form "relationship(a,b, . . . , n)". Examples of such a logical relationships are "conferred_by(susceptibility(ALS24), mutation(chromosome(4q33)))", "identify(substitution, gene)", "described_in(Siddique_Deng_1996, autosomal_inheritance)". Please do not write full sentences.

This prompt should enable us to derive logical links in somewhat complex forms, including predicates with unrestricted arity, and predicates of predicates. We devised an iterative Python procedure to run the LLM prompt on each line of the OMIM entry [#613679](#), then another Python procedure in order to parse the results and only keep the sentences that were correctly translated into logical summaries. Interestingly, the educational way of wording the prompt encouraged the chatbot to generate us replies that tended to use the words: "Question:" and "Answer:", so those replies had to be filtered out.

Figure 2: Hackathon results: the *OMIMSummarize* project for clinicians and patients in 3 phases.

Using MistralAI, we retrieved 46 logic links for the OMIM webpage about hypoprothrombinemia. Code and results are provided in Supplementary Material. Literature provenance can be expressed using our logical relationships:

```
reported(Inomoto_et_al_1987, dysprothrombinemia_variants)
identified_by(Poort_et_al_1994, mutation(F2_gene_Y44C))
```

The results of summarizing long OMIM descriptive texts into logical relationships with Hugging-Face and MistralAI are about exactly as expected. For instance, the LLM is able to derive us the prevalence of the disease, its heritability, and its main characteristics as logical associations.

```
affects_about(prothrombin_deficiency, 1_in_2_000_000_individuals)
inheritance_pattern(autosomal_recessive, Josso_et_al_1962, first_cousins)
characterized_by(prothrombin_deficiency, low_levels_of_prothrombin)
```

In another conversation reply, the chatbot was able to generate the predicate 'caused_by' and to associate the correct protein defects to the correct disease variants.

```
caused_by(defect_in_activation, prothrombin_Barcelona),
caused_by(defect_in_protease, prothrombin_Quick),
caused_by(defect_in_protease, prothrombin_Tokushima)
```

Thanks to the generative model, a clinician will be able to correctly infer that *e.g.* the literature for assessing that the disease is autosomal recessive is Josso et al, 1962, and that at least three disease variants exist: called Barcelona, Quick and Tokushima.

In conclusion, this two-phase procedure allowed to summarize the phenotypes associated to diseases described in the OMIM database. In long-term, the aforementioned third phase could be integrated and made accessible to a clinician. We represent the full project in Figure 2.

Discussion

Automatic summarization is an important task for computer intelligences to perform in information retrieval. Here, we were able to find a good LLM prompt for generating summaries of OMIM pages as logical relationships that could be used in automatic reasoning. Similar work was performed, outside of the medical summary context, in (Yang et al., 2023). Eager to develop our ideas further than the Hackathon, we coined our prospective tool *OMIMSummarize*.

Our starting point was a simple observation: the OMIM (Online Mendelian Inheritance in Man) database offers very exhaustive information on certain diseases entered by clinicians. It can therefore be difficult for clinicians to obtain the information they want to see or check (e.g. finding a bibliographic reference) in a quick and comprehensible way. In this paper we aim to prototype a targeted and reliable computational tool that will help the clinician to access - from a given symptom or disease respectively - the associated diseases or symptoms. In other words, from the symptoms of any patient we would like to infer which disease they could possibly display. Ideally, formal logic links between rare diseases and phenotypes should be supplemented by experimental proofs or formal models, such as this metabolic modelling

study (Siharath et al., 2024). We argue in that regard that *in silico* models are complementary to *in vitro* and *in vivo* models.

In the context of precision medicine, we hope that *OMIMSummarize* will facilitate access to the up-to-date OMIM reference database and thus encourage its use by clinicians in all relevant specialties. Detailed logical summaries of the webpages will enable medical staff to keep abreast of new disease-gene-phenotype associations - with a view to refining and/or confirming their diagnoses. Indeed, automated reasoning - once the model has been consolidated and corrected - can be used to graphically connect the possible links between genes, symptoms and several diseases, and apply it on patient records for systematic assessments. Once the information has been proposed by our tool, the clinician will be able to check how the tool has generated such a response, and will therefore have a view on explainability.

However, the method currently developed presents the major drawback of being based on LLMs for the first phase, which are 1) black-box and 2) capable of hallucinations. In contrast, using a deterministic syntactic decomposition-based method for phase 1 would allow us to have a fully explainable method from start to finish. Therefore we could have a guarantee that the logic links generated by phase 1 and used for automatic reasoning in phase 3 are correctly summarized from the text and not hallucinated with probable words from outside of it. In the next section we explore why formal explanations could be the most ethical solution, especially for the medical domain where AI getting things wrong could cost a life.

The necessity of formal explanations

Neurosymbolic Artificial Intelligence is a subfield of AI which attempts to combine machine learning, performed by Neural Networks, with symbolic knowledge representation and formal logic reasoning (Garcez & Lamb, 2020). The former, neural intelligence, represents the newest wave of deep learning using massive amounts of data, while the latter, symbolic reasoning, represents the earlier wave of artificial intelligence, using formal thinking with carefully crafted 'expert systems' from 'expert knowledge'.

This duality between machine learning and artificial intelligence is interesting as it underlines the needs of the scientific community: despite the impressive size neural networks can reach today, and the striking reasoning capacities of Large Language Models, their black-box, statistical, probabilistic nature might hinder them from truly thinking like an expert of the domain (Bedi et al., 2024; Goh et al., 2024; Hagendorff, 2024).

And a vital feature of a capable artificial intelligence would be the ability to explain its reasoning. Several approaches to explainability in large statistical analyzes of data involve shifting the paradigm to Bayesian statistics, where models are more explicit and uncertainty can be quantified (Ni et al., 2022). Other approaches to explainability involve using appropriate data structures, such as decision trees. Decision trees present the remarkable features of offering exact explanations by simply reading paths up to the leaf on the trees (Therneau et al., 2023).

Here, we advocate for the usage of formal explainable solutions. Marques-Silva and Ignatiev define the field of formal explainable AI (fxAI) as artificial intelligence that is explained fully by symbolic approaches (Marques-Silva & Ignatiev, 2022). They tackled the problem of explaining boosted decision trees, and showed that heuristic approaches proposed by the literature failed whereas their formal logic-based solutions succeeded (Ignatiev et al., 2019a, 2019b). Related work has also been performed by the teams of Audemard and Marquis (Audemard et al., 2022). Oftentimes, formal explanations also need to be minimal. The requirement for minimal interpretable features to explain a model follows Ockham's razor principle. In fact, one of the authors of this paper worked on getting minimal mathematical features of metabolic network models. It turns out the set of minimal explanatory features is more difficult to compute but more convenient for human interpretation.

Intrinsically, this is why we chose to turn to formal explanations for *OMIMSummarize*, with the minimal justification trees of s(CASP) (Arias et al., 2020). Our approach acts as a counterpart to the increasing use of black-box neural learning techniques, that are devoid of explainability.

We would want the medical community to use formal logic and automated reasoning tools to automatically derive what illnesses patients can have from their symptoms, not to use ChatGPT to summarize the medical information.

Conclusions

We devised a draft project for the tool *OMIMSummarize*, worked on during a Hackathon project. We were able to reconstruct logic links from summaries, in particular for the hypoprothrombinemia disease. OMIM contains many data about genetics and symptoms of rare diseases. Yet its webpages are too information-rich compared to the time a clinician has for its diagnoses. While OMIM already provides logic relationships in the form of ontologies, they are not complete enough nor easily useable to derive diagnoses for patients. Therefore clinicians would be tempted to retrieve the information they need using Large Language Models. We argue that ChatGPT and other chatbots create text in a way that is not explainable, while diagnosis with automated reasoning on logic links would allow explainability. Further work on syntactic decomposition is necessary to provide a tool that is as few dependent on neural intelligence as possible.

Data and code availability

Code associated to this study and resulting output are available in Supplementary Material to this article.

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